

Design and Fabrication of Mobile Hydropower Plant

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Abstract - In this modern world where mostly everything needs power to operate and this power is achieved through different resources, using different techniques. The main resources of power production is coal, hydro, nuclear & solar, but in most cases the resources and methods used for production are not eco-friendly like coal burning & nuclear procedures etc. Moreover on hilly areas where most of the people are deprived of electricity likewise on the camping spots, where tourists needs affordable and easily available power. In this context, the objective of this work is to make power available on such sites by using eco-friendly, cost effective and easy method to facilitates the tourists & local community. The proposed study focuses on the direct river flow to produce energy on the basis of emergency power demands. More specifically, in this work we provide scientific arguments on how the energy issue can be readily resolved and then design and fabricate a mobile hydropower plant for this purpose. It has been calculated that the adoption of mobile hydropower plant in Pakistan can save upto 120 million tonnes of coal or 83.3 billion liters of oil annually. Furthermore, these plants are environmentally friendly and make a low contribution to global warming.

Keywords – Hydropower Plant, Sustainable Energy, Commercialization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy is a fundamental human requirement and a key factor in socioeconomic development. The world's energy needs are rising quickly as a result of the world's population and industrialization both growing quickly. Due to their excessive consumption, conventional energy sources including petroleum, coal, and nuclear are being depleted as a result of the growth in energy demand. In addition to polluting the environment and upsetting the ecosystem's balance, fossil fuels also cause these problems. Since fossil fuels are the predominant energy source in Pakistan, the country's power industry is also the largest source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Using fossil fuels to generate power and heat resulted in the emission of 54.5 million tonnes of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in 2017. Fossil fuel-based power plants emit CO₂, in addition to noise, vibration, heat, sulphur dioxide (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and particulates. While NO_x weakens the ozone layer, atmospheric CO₂ contributes to global warming. In addition to harming human health and causing acid rain, SO₂ also degrades materials and vegetation and may reduce visibility. 12,000 Pakistanis suffer each year as a result of air pollution. On the other side, unconventional renewable energy resources (RERs) like geothermal, wind, sun, tidal from the ocean, and hydro are abundant, unrenueable, and clean. Due to the depletion of fossil fuels and the escalating rate of GHG emissions, many nations are transitioning to RERs. Hydropower is the most significant RER for the production of electric power globally, meeting 19% of the world's energy needs.

The global electrical energy problem, particularly in Pakistan, is a significant issue right now. Power shortages last 10 to 12 hours in urban areas and 14 to 20 hours in rural areas each day because of a shortage of electricity. The demand for electricity currently stands at 15,000 MW, and by 2050 it is anticipated to reach 49,078 MW. The need for energy cannot be satisfied by conventional energy sources. Pakistan is currently experiencing an energy crisis, primarily as a result of insufficient electricity additions to the power infrastructure. Population expansion, rapid industrialization, and a high rate of urbanization are some of the variables that contribute to energy dilemma. The country's gross domestic product has been impacted, production has been halted, and citizens' social lives have

suffered as a result of the energy crisis. Due to factory closures caused by the energy crisis, unemployment has also increased. The energy crisis has now impacted Pakistan's national security.

Till date, numerous researches have been carried out in the field of hydropower plants. Ying-bin Liang et al. work on straight bladed vertical axis wind turbine [1]. They investigated the blade profile for the aerodynamics performance, including thickness, camber, leading/trailing edge and roughness. Another challenge for them was to identify the design parameters like swept area, supporting arms, solidity ration etc. They tested different blades including, NACA0012, NACA0015 and NACA0018. Out of these, NACA0018 was preferred due high power coefficient and self-starting capacity. Aguilar et al. studied both numerical and experimental approach [2]. This work is conducted for two horizontal axis wind hydro-kinetic turbine: with and without multi element hydrofoil cross section. They have used Eppler 420 and obtained maximum power coefficient (C_{pmax}) 0.5050 and 0.419 at TSR 0.7129 and 0.419 for multi-element hydrofoil and without multi-element respectively. The multi-element hydrofoil Eppler 420 produced 20.53% more C_p as compared to traditional Eppler 420 hydrofoil. Zaid Hammoudi et al. have done CFD analysis on vertical axis hydro-kinetic wind turbine [3]. The main objectives was to investigate the effect of hydrofoil on the performance of Darrieus-type vertical-axis turbine and the interaction between two axially aligned turbines. They conducted for two hydrofoils: NACA0018 and NACA4415. Of which NACA0018 hydrofoils produced highest torque and thus more power. They also investigated for TSR of 1 and 2, which shows its importance and can reverse the behaviour of the HKT.

Hantoro et al. carried out numerical as well as experimental study on the vertical axis hydro-kinetic turbine in three configurations: 3 bladed, 6 bladed and 9 bladed NACA0018 [4]. Their work confirmed that model 3; 9 bladed hydro-kinetic had C_p reached to 0.42. Muratoglu et al. designed 1 hp hydro-kinetic for water velocity 1.5 m/s with TSR 6.325, an angle of attack (AOA) 5° and 0° pitch angle. They used S822 airfoil and got maximum power coefficient of 0.4382 [5]. Ramirez et al. designed 500W vertical axis hydro-kinetic turbine with diameter 1.5 m and height (span) of 1.13 m for river application with velocity 1.5 m/s [6]. They used NACA0025 with cord length 0.33 m, three bladed and solidity ratio of 0.66. They also used 6 bladed (model 2) and 9 bladed (model 3) turbine. Model 1, 2 and 3 gave power coefficient of 0.25, 0.51 and 0.55 respectively. In this study model 2 is preferred due less torque fluctuation. Malge et al. worked on vertical axis wind turbine with introduction of plastic gear [7]. This is important modification, because dynamo available in the market requires high revolution to produce the required power, which fulfill this requirement. They also introduced bearing in their design for easy rotation and reduction of noise. Further research work in this area are available as: [8-16].

This research demonstrates how Small Hydro Power Plants (SHPPs) might help ease the electricity crisis in some areas. In Pakistan, hydropower resources of 60,000 MW have been found. While just 7228 MW of the listed resources—or around 11 percent of them—are now providing electricity. By deploying SHPPs, the energy situation can be readily resolved. It has been calculated that the adoption of SHPPs can save 120 million tonnes of coal or 83.3 billion liters of oil annually. Thus, these plants are environmentally friendly and make a low contribution to global warming.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II present the design calculation and CAD model of the hydropower plant. Fabrication process is presented in section III. Conclusion and some future work are given in section IV.

II. DESIGN CALCULATIONS AND CAD MODEL

The first step in the design calculations for the hydropower plant is to measure the water flow rate of the river on which the powerplant is to be designed. This flow rate is then used as a basis to calculate the other parameters. The selected river in the project is 'Swat River at KPK, Pakistan' where the water flow rate was calculated by two methods; 1. Using flow meter, 2. By letting a small light bob between the two setted points of fixed distances in river. As the bob is released from starting point the time is noted by stop watch till the bob reaches the second point, travelling a fixed distance in specific interval of time. This method is repeated 10 times at different spots of the river and readings are being recorded, thus the final value of the river velocity is the average of readings taken. So the average velocity obtained by both the method approximately 1.3 m/s.

2.1 Shaft Diameter –

As velocity of water = $V = 1.3$ m/s and density of the water = 1000kg/m^3

Let; swept area of the turbine = $A = d \times h = 0.5 \times 0.6 = 0.306 \text{ m}^2$ for 100 rpm = $(100 \times 2 \times \pi)/60 = 1034 \text{ rad/s}$

length of shaft = 0.7m

So, water power = $\frac{1}{2} \times \rho \times A \times v^3 = \frac{1}{2} (1000 \times 0.3036 \times 1.3^3) = 333.50$ watt
Turbine power = 0.3 * water power = 100 watt

Torque = $P/w = 100/10.46 = 9.56$ Nm

Force on shaft = $F = T/r = 9.56/0.25 = 38.24$ N

Bending moment = $M = F \times L/2 = 38.24 \times 0.7 = 13.384$ Nm

Diameter of the shaft: Using max shear stress theory:

$$D = \{(0.04889)/10^6 \times 16.45\}^{0.33}$$

For factor of safety = 2

$$D = 10.86\text{mm} = 11\text{mm}$$

2.2 Bearing Selection –

For selecting a specific bearing from the bearing manufacturer's catalog, some parameters should be defined, derived as follows:

Let dynamo weight = 4kg, Collective weight of foils + shaft + strips = 2kg, Dummy load = 4 kg: total load = 10kg

Thus, axial force on the bearing (F_a) is = $10 \times 9.81 = 98.1$ N

Radial force $F_r = (W \times w_2 \times r) / g = (19.6 \times 10.462 \times 0.25)/9.81 = 54.68$ N

Now equivalent force $F_e = X V F_r + Y F_a = 225.83$ N

$C_{10} = L^{0.33} \times F_e = (200 \text{ million})^{0.33} \times 225.83 = 1320\text{N} = 300$ lb

As $C_r > C$ from bearing no = 6801, $F_a/C_o = (98.1/4.45)/233 = 0.0946$

From manufacturer's catalog we will use $X = 0.56$ $Y = 1.51$ therefore, $F_e = 0.56(54.68) + 1.51(98.1) = 178.75\text{N}$

$C_{10} = 178.75(200)^{0.333}$ $C_{10} = 1045\text{N} = 234.9\text{lb}$

The selected bearing from the series 68800 is:

Bearing No: 6801, d(mm): 12, D (mm): 21, B(mm): 5

2.3 Frame Calculation –

Force on each supporting rod, $F = 49\text{N}$

$F_{\text{critical}} = \pi^2 EI / (KL)^2$, $49 = \{3.142 \times (190\text{GPa}) \times 3.14 \times d^4/64\} / 0.7\text{m}$, **$d_o = 0.00439\text{m} = 4.3\text{mm}$**

Using above equation for hollow shaft we get: **$d_i = 5.8\text{mm}$**

2.4 Blade Chord Length –

The Tip speed ratio, $\lambda = (w * r) / V = (45 \times 2\pi/60 \text{ rad/s})(0.25)/(1.3 \text{ m/s}) = 0.9057$

Using λ & solving for the solidity ratio(σ), $\sigma = 1.2374$

For four blades: $\sigma = NC/D$, **C= 15.4cm = 6in**

For three blades: $\sigma = NC/D$, **C = 206mm = 8.24in**

Note: increasing the number of blades result in increasing the flow disturbance caused by the adjacent blade to the upcoming blade in that direction.

2.5 CAD Model –

To design the whole model of hydro power plant two designs were suggested to get the whole picture of the model, each individual component of 1:1 scale were designed in CAD then specific material properties were applied to specified component in order to reflect the actual model and to help fabricate the model. Then using assembly window to assemble the individual components to get the required design. The top and front side inclined view of the final model is shown in figure 1 and 2 respectively.

Figure 1. Top view of final model

Figure 2. From side inclined view of final model

III. FABRICATION

During the fabrication of the mobile hydro power plant, different processes are applied to form a final shape of the design. Following are the processes adopted in fabrication of the mobile hydro power plant.

3.1 Cutting –

During the fabrication of mobile hydro power plant we used cutting machine to cut the metal pipes of the desired measurements.

- We cut metal pipe of 48 inches of length for shaft.
- We cut 8 number of horizontal supporting arms of 11 inches of length.
- Then we cut 4 number of vertical supporting arms of 26 inches of length.
- After that we cut 6 number of strips of length 10 inches.
- Then we cut bearing holding rings.
- After that we cut 2 rings for the strips attachment purpose.
- We cut strips for dynamo support arrangements.

- Excess material from clips were cut down for proper joining.
- We took plank and cut it into three each having length of 21 inches for hydrofoils.
- Then we draw the profile of the hydrofoil on the plank and cut excess material.

3.2 Surface Grinding and Drilling –

Grinding process was performed on all the pre-cut components such as supporting arms, rotating shaft, bearing holders, bearing arrangements and strips holders. For internal grinding we use bench voice for holding the component and then performed grinding by multi-functional electric grinder. The surface grinding is done on the turbine foils. For that we took plank and draw the profile of the hydrofoil on the plank. Then perform grinding using grit papers to get the finish surface. Furthermore, drilling operation is performed almost in every component to join them through Nuts and bolts like in the blades, bar strips, & frame pipes etc. This operation is done by the bench and hand drilling machine.

3.3 Welding and Final Assembling –

Arc welding was performed on bearings and its regarding holder. After that we welded clips to the bearing ring. Afterwards, the rings to which strips to be attached were weld at specified position. We then welded that bearings to the shaft with proper alignment and clips to the supporting arms. At the end, we welded the dynamo supporting arrangement with one of the supporting arm of the turbine. In assembling of mobile hydro power plant, we use nuts and bolts to join each component with another by its respective position as shown as final assembly in figure 3 and 4:

- First we joined horizontal supporting arms to the bearing holding rings by means of clips that were welded to them before, with the help of nuts and bolts.
- Then the vertical supporting arms were joined to the horizontal arms with the help of nuts and bolts.
- After that we took off step for joining the strips to the rings which were welded to shaft having three clips welded at equal angle.
- A small pulley of about 2.5 inches were attached to the dynamo.
- We then attach dynamo with the help of nuts and bolts to the supporting arrangements of dynamo.
- Then we fix the shaft pulley to the shaft at specific position.
- Belt and pulley arrangement were made between shaft and dynamo.
- Then we attached foils to the strips with the help of screws and fixed its angle of attack.

Figure 3. Final assembly of hydropower plant

Figure 4. Hydropower plant under test

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

By testing the hydropower plant at Swat River, KP, Pakistan we got 45rpm. By providing specific rpm. i-e the shaft rotates with 45rpm, a pulley is attached with shaft and belted with dynamo, which increases the rpm to dynamo by 3 times as: $45 \times 3 = 135\text{rpm}$, to obtain power of 100watt and more. It was concluded that a minimum of 2200 rpm is

required, so the dynamo is consisting of gears which converts the input rpm by (1:17) to output rpm (135 x 17 = 2295rpm), thus the required rpm was achieved and power of 126 watts is produced with this prototype.

We further conclude that the following factors make the Mobile Hydro Powerplant a good product choice to be commercialized in local markets:

- The turbine has light weight of 10kg & compact design which leads to requirement of less efforts to carry it from one spot to another i.e it is light weighted and portable as compared to conventional hydro powerplants.
- This turbine is straightforward function able, an unskillful person can effortlessly operate it.
- The mobile hydropower plant having total cost of 40k and almost no maintenance costs makes it more attractive choice economically, as conventional hydro powerplants having very high initial & maintenance costs.
- Mobile hydropower plant is applicable for all types of locations (mountain's water flow, ground level channels & rivers, and specially on tourist's spots). Due to a lot of these characteristics, it attracts client interest.

In the future, the overall size of the turbine can be increased so that to increase the net power output, as the river flow is greater so increasing the overall size would make turbine able to extract maximum possible energy from flowing water. Moreover, Increasing the overall size of the turbine would allow the designer & manufacturer to adjust more number of blades of greater chord lengths, by this solidity ratio would increase which results in lower tip speed ratio i.e. it would make the turbine further feasible for lower velocity flows.

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